

Improving Healthcare Services through Reducing Zero-Stock Reports in PHCs Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Quality improvement initiative to reduce zero stock items through improved demand supply chain system in primary healthcare centers.

Aim: This study aims to explore strategies and evaluate the effectiveness of the digitalized demand supply chain for reducing zero stock incidents in PHC settings and how these reductions can improve the quality of care provided to patients.

Method: A quantitative data collection on Zero stock incidents was conducted in all primary healthcare facilities over 24 months. Comparing the frequency of zero-stock items reports from before and after implementing the digitalized demand supply chain system.

Result: The findings suggest that the new supply chain system has contributed to improving inventory management and reduced instances of zero-stock, ultimately enhancing the availability of essential supplies in PHCs.

Conclusion: Quantitative analysis of zero stock reports over two years reveals that effective supply chain management and targeted interventions significantly reduce zero stock reports in PHC facilities.

More Information

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Keywords:

demand-supply, medical supplies, inventory, supply chain system, quality improvement, PHC services.

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Introduction

Primary health care (PHC) services are from the foundation of health systems worldwide, providing essential health services such as preventive care, treatment, and management of chronic diseases. PHC centers health care services require a supply of essential medical supplies and medications. Zero stock incidents can result from several factors including poor supply chain management, inefficient inventory systems, inadequate forecasting, limited supplier performance, and delayed procurement processes. One of the challenges faced by PHC facilities is the occurrence of zero-stock incidents, which refers to the unavailability of essential medical supplies and medications. Research has demonstrated that when PHC facilities experience zero stock incidents, it leads to long wait times for patients, decreased patient satisfaction, and in severe cases, the need for emergency referrals or hospitalizations. Zero stock incidents negatively impact the quality of care, patient

satisfaction, and health outcomes. Various strategies have been proposed to mitigate zero-stock incidents, such as improved forecasting, automated inventory systems, and policies that prioritize the consistent delivery of essential supplies.

Review of Literature

In many settings, primary care, which is the first contact of people with health services that are continuous, comprehensive & coordinated, has too often, been focused on treating illness as and when it arises rather than preventing disease in the first place [1]. The center provides primary health care services to the region it serves based on comprehensive care for family medicine. Through it, they provide educational, preventive, and curative services which include: urgent care, scheduled care, preventive care, maternity & pediatric care, chronic disease care & school curative and preventive health for surrounding schools [2]. Understanding the need for health care, and how this differs from the need for health that under pins it, is an

important step towards quantifying current demand for health care and its future trends. It also supports decisions on the amount and type of resources the health care system requires, such as the medical and non-medical workforce and infrastructure (supply) [3]. The demand for health care is different from demand for other goods or services. The demand for health care is a derived demand arising from the fundamental demand for good health that is required for consumption and investment purposes [4]. Supply will vary over time and across geographies due to changes in the size of the budget, the production technology and the availability of scarce resources such as health care professionals. Treatments supplied range from those that are proven to be cost-effective for a particular condition to those for which there is no evidence of effectiveness or cost-effectiveness [5]. A healthcare supply chain that functions at an optimal level can increase resilience, improve patient care, and raise physician satisfaction [6]. The supply chain generally refers to the resources needed to deliver goods or services to a consumer. Therefore, healthcare supply chain management involves obtaining resources, managing supplies, and delivering goods and services to providers and patients [7]. The design and management of a supply chain seek to obtain the best global performances so as to achieve the better performance of single link of the chain [8]. The benefits of supply chain is when hospitals effectively manage the movement of goods from manufacturers and suppliers to providers, it can help them to streamline processes, maximize operating efficiency, and minimize waste [6]. Keeping inventory in check with supply chain management can ensure that hospitals can track inventory to quickly identify possible shortages or any other issues with product availability. As a result, well-priced medical devices and supplies will be available when healthcare professionals need them [6]. Inventory management is vital as it helps maintain a steady supply to patients, hence preventing product stock out, while minimizing the costs of holding inventory. Accurate and updated stock records are crucial for proper inventory management since they are input to calculate future needs. Holding stocks is

important to ensure availability of essential items almost all the time [9]. Implementing periodic review order-up to level servicing approach is one of the distinctive features of material management in a hospital. A major issue in setting order-up to level for different items in a healthcare system is that these levels tend to reflect the desired inventory levels of the patient caregivers rather than the actual inventory levels needed in a department over a certain period [10]. The digitalization of the supply chain can be defined as the exploitation of the capacities of traditional information systems and the implementation of new advanced technologies, big data, augmented reality, unmanned aerial vehicles, and blockchain to make the different activities of the supply chain more flexible and efficient. Digitization initiatives in hospitals focus mainly on the implementation of classic technologies such as enterprise resource programs (ERP) and electronic data interchange (EDI) for the integration of the supply chain [10].

Methods

A pre-post intervention study for the reports of zero stock items in PHC. Data were collected During 2023, then the intervention was implemented by the end of 2023. Then data were collected for the 2024 zero stock reports. A comparison of the rates and proportions was done. Descriptive statistics and graphic presentations were produced. So, A quantitative data collection on ZERO stock incidents was conducted in all primary healthcare facilities over 24 months. Comparing the frequency of zero-stock items reports from before and after the implementation of the digitalized demand supply chain system.

Results

The bar graph illustrates the comparison of zero-stock items reported over the years 2023 and 2024 (see Figure 1). In 2023, there was a noticeable shift as new digitalized demand supply chain systems were implemented, leading to a change in the data. The graph showed an upward trend in 2023 reflecting the impact of these implementations. By 2024, the data will stabilize highlighting the ongoing effects of the new demand supply chain system.

Figure 1: Frequence Bar Chart of Zero Item Reports 2023-2024

The digitalized demand supply chain system implemented by the end of 2023 and actively used in the year 2024. Figure 1 shows descriptive statistics of frequency notes such as bar graphs for each month of 2023 and 2024. We noticed an overall reduction of zero-stock item reports in 2024 compared to 2023. The zero-stock item reported in 2024 was 17 compared to 2023 with 25 zero-stock items, on average. There was a 32% decrease in the average number of zero-stock items from 2023 to 2024. This indicates a significant improvement in stock management or the impact of the digitalized supply chain system implemented in 2023.

Conclusion

Reducing zero stock incidents in PHC facilities is a crucial step toward improving the quality of health services. This study demonstrated that an integrated approach to inventory management can effectively reduce zero stocks, enhance patient care, and lead to better clinical outcomes. Further research is needed to explore the long-term sustainability and scalability of the intervention. Adopting a system of visually inspecting requested stock items increased the efficiency of the demand-supply chain system and reduced the frequency of zero-stock items. A centralized system provides real-time visibility in stock levels, enabling more effective management of inventory and quicker responses to low-stock alerts. Limitations of this research is that it is short duration (24 months) it may not capture long-term impacts and it is limited to PHC facilities, which may not fully represent the diversity of healthcare settings

References

[1] Beard JR, Bloom B. Towards a comprehensive public health response to population ageing. *Lancet*. 2014;385:658-61. doi:10.1016/s0140-6736(14)61461-6

[2] MOH Guide to excellence: in primary health care center services. Available from <http://www.moh.gov.sa/Documents.MOH-Guide-to-Exellenece-English.pdf>. Accessed on 14 Sep 2024.

[3] Aday LA and Andersen R (1974) A framework for the study of access to medical care. *Health Services Research* 9, 208-22

[4] Grossman M (1972) On the concept of health capital and the demand for health. *Journal of Political Economy* 80, 223-255

[5] Idaira Rodriguez Santana et al. Article: Need, demand, supply in health care: working definitions, and their implications for defining access. *Health Economics Policy and Law* 18(1). Page 6. Available from http://www.researchgate.net/publication/355212238_Need_demand_supply_in_health_care_working_definitions_and_their_implications_for_defining_access. Accessed on 13 Sep 2024.

[6] www.apu.apus.edu. The Importance of Supply Chain Management in Healthcare. *Nursing and Health Sciences Blog*. American Public University. Available from <http://www.apu.apus.edu/area-of-study/nursing-and-health-sciences/resources/the-importance-of-supply-chain-management-in-healthcare>. Accessed on 06 Sep 2024.

[7] Jacqueline LaPointe. Featured Article: Exploring the Role of Supply Chain Management in Healthcare. *www.techtarget.com xtelligent Rev Cycle Management*. Available from <http://www.techtarget.com/revcyclemanagement/feature/Exploring-the-Role-of-Supply-Chain-Management-in-Healthcare>. Accessed on 12 Sep 2024.

[8] AslamT.,Ng A.H.C. 2010. Multi-objective Optimization for Supply Chain Management: a Literature Review and New Development. *SCMIS 8th International Conference on Supply Chain Management and Information Systems*, 6-9 October 2010. 1-8.

[9] Management Science for Health, MDS-3: managing access to medicines and health technologies. Arlington: MSH; 2012. Available from <https://www.msh.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/01/mds3-jan2014.pdf>. Accessed on 15 Sep 2024.

[10] Ncholson L., Vakharia A.J. and Erenguc S. S, (2004). *European Journal of Operational Research*, 154, 271-290.

[11] Beaulieu M., Bentahar O., 2021. Digitalization of the healthcare supply chain: A roadmap to generate benefits and effectively support healthcare delivery. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* Volume 167. Available from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0040162521001499>. Accessed on 13 Sep 2024.

